

GOALS AND TECHNIQUES FOR TEACHING GRAMMAR

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Abstract:

The article describes the role of grammar in teaching and developing speaking skills, critical thinking of students in the lessons). As the goal of grammar instruction is to enable students to carry out their communication purposes

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Goals and Techniques for Teaching Grammar:

First of all, let me tell why do we need grammar? Many students ask me about advantages of grammar. Or can they learn only grammar without learning words? I always answer that without learning words you cannot use grammar, and vice versa without learning grammar you cannot make up sentences. As Jumayeva Sh. Sh. said in her articles “Teaching children is a challenge. They are fidget. They like to play. Let them play though they are students. Let them be children as even teacher is a child in the heart. As I have been working as a teacher I understood what it is to be creative and communicative, well-educated and intelligent. Yes, teaching helps to understand it. If teacher wants children to learn English or to be interested in English she must work hard and try to use new methods of involving students. As we know year by year students are getting independent, full of energy, but not knowing how to use this independence and energy is bringing to the loss of very “genius” children. Most members of the language teaching profession realize that their students’ learning potential increases when attitudes are positive and motivations runs high. And it is on the hand of teachers.” (Jumayeva Shahlo Shokirovna, “Drills and Dialogues in English Lessons”, International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education, Volume 4, Issue 1, Page Number 40-43, 2019.)

So what is the goal of grammar learning? The goal of grammar instruction is to enable students to carry out their communication purposes. This goal has three implications:

- Students need overt instruction that connects grammar points with larger communication contexts.
- Students do not need to master every aspect of each grammar point, only those that are relevant to the immediate communication task.
- Error correction is not always the instructor's first responsibility.

Overt Grammar Instruction:

Adult students appreciate and benefit from direct instruction that allows them to apply critical thinking skills to language learning. Instructors can take advantage of this by providing explanations that give students a descriptive understanding (declarative knowledge) of each point of grammar. Teach the grammar point in the target language or the students' first language or both. The goal is to facilitate understanding. Limit the time you devote to grammar explanations to 10 minutes, especially for lower level students whose ability to sustain attention can be limited. Present grammar points in written and oral ways to address the needs of students with different learning styles. An important part of grammar instruction is providing examples. Teachers need to plan their examples carefully around two basic principles:

Be sure the examples are accurate and appropriate. They must present the language appropriately, be culturally appropriate for the setting in which they are used, and be to the point of the lesson. Use the examples as teaching tools. Focus examples on a particular theme or topic so that students have more contact with specific information and vocabulary.

Relevance of Grammar Instruction:

In the communicative competence model, the purpose of learning grammar is to learn the language of which the grammar is a part. Instructors therefore teach grammar forms and structures in relation to meaning and use for the specific communication tasks that students need to complete. Compare the traditional model and the communicative competence model for teaching the English past tense:

Traditional: grammar for grammar's sake

Teach the regular -ed form with its two pronunciation variants

Teach the doubling rule for verbs that end in d (for example, wed-wedded)

Hand out a list of irregular verbs that students must memorize

Do pattern practice drills for -ed

Do substitution drills for irregular verbs

Communicative competence: grammar for communication's sake

Distribute two short narratives about recent experiences or events, each one to half of the class

Teach the regular -ed form, using verbs that occur in the texts as examples. Teach the pronunciation and doubling rules if those forms occur in the texts.

Teach the irregular verbs that occur in the texts.

Students read the narratives, ask questions about points they don't understand.

Students work in pairs in which one member has read Story A and the other Story B. Students interview one another; using the information from the interview, they then write up or orally repeat the story they have not read.

Error Correction:

At all proficiency levels, learners produce language that is not exactly the language used by native speakers. Some of the differences are grammatical, while others involve vocabulary selection and mistakes in the selection of language appropriate for different contexts. In responding to student communication, teachers need to be careful not to focus on error correction to the detriment of communication and confidence building. Teachers need to let students know when they are making errors so that they can work on improving. Teachers also need to build students' confidence in their ability to use the language by focusing on the content of their communication rather than the grammatical form.

Teachers can use error correction to support language acquisition, and avoid using it in ways that undermine students' desire to communicate in the language, by taking cues from context. When students are doing structured output activities that focus on development of new language skills, use error correction to guide them. Example:

Student (in class): I buy a new car yesterday.

Teacher: You bought a new car yesterday. Remember, the past tense of buy is bought.

When students are engaged in communicative activities, correct errors only if they interfere with comprehensibility. Respond using correct forms, but without stressing them. Example:

Student (greeting teacher): I buy a new car yesterday!

Teacher: You bought a new car? That's exciting! What kind?

As Jumayeva Sh. Sh. said in her articles the grammar also can be used in the role plays. "Grammar as a Basis for Role Plays. Another basis for role plays is for practicing structures. Because role plays are less controlled than drills and dialogues, it is important to choose situations and contexts in which the target structure occurs naturally. For example, courtroom role plays work well for less-controlled practice of past and past-progressive tense, and for question formation. Roles usually include the judge, the lawyers for the defense and the prosecution, clients, and witnesses. Each student is assigned a role and each is played out during the trial.

Remember that because role plays are less controlled practice activities, students may not use the target structures as much as you would like. There are usually several ways to successfully communicate meaning, so consider role play as an opportunity for students to practice a range of speaking and listening skills, rather than a single structure. In each of these situations, you can develop the role play or you can do so with your students. With some experience, students can write their own scripts for role plays."

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